

STATE REGULATION OF THE FOOD SECTOR - THE BASIS FOR ENSURING FOOD SAFETY

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Abstract: This article examines the methods and tasks of state regulation of the food market to ensure food safety. It also analyzes state policy and its results in regulating the food market.

Key words: *food security, development of agriculture, food market, food policy, regulating the production of food, to increase agricultural production*

Food security is one of the most important components of national security, as it ensures the sustainable production of basic products related to the state's food resources and the continuous and equal use of these products by the population. Ensuring food security also serves to ensure economic stability within the country, maintaining the social well-being of society. To this end, the state has developed and implemented various programs for the development of territories and the regulation of agriculture. These programs, in turn, include a number of regulatory methods aimed at ensuring the effective and sustainable development of agriculture:

- regulation of the volume of production, agricultural acreage and specialization of territories in the regions;
- creation of social and market infrastructure in the countryside;
- improvement of the reclamation condition of agricultural lands;
- improvement and strengthening of the material and technical base of agricultural enterprises, creation of a network of enterprises for the provision of production services;
- construction of nature protection and hydraulic installations;
- financial support for loss-making and low-profit agricultural enterprises.

In accordance with the programs implemented to deepen economic reforms in agriculture, the processes of forming the property class and developing farms in rural areas are continuing. These processes are aimed at increasing the efficiency of agriculture, strengthening the competitiveness of local production, and ensuring economic stability. At the same time, necessary measures are being taken to improve soil fertility, modernize selection and seed production, increase crop yields, and raise the quality of agricultural products to a high level.

The goal is to make farms more efficient by providing them with the necessary financial, technical and knowledge resources. Such reforms serve not only to increase production volumes, but also to introduce innovative approaches in agriculture.

In addition, special attention is paid to increasing soil fertility. This includes the use of advanced land reclamation technologies to preserve and restore soil fertility, and the creation of environmentally sustainable production systems. By improving breeding and seed production, it is possible to improve the quality of agricultural products, develop new varieties, and grow existing crops more efficiently. All this makes it possible to increase agricultural production volumes, supply high-quality and competitive products not only to the domestic market, but also to the international market.

Taking into account the current state of the Uzbek food market, the state's food policy should be directed towards the following areas:

- stabilizing the production of grain, meat, milk and other basic food products, as well as bringing them to a level that meets domestic needs. this, in turn, includes regulating the food market and creating the necessary reserve fund, forming insurance reserves and ensuring optimal supply of commodity resources.

- structural restructuring of agricultural production and its orientation in accordance with consumer needs. this includes efforts to modernize production processes and improve the quality of agricultural products.

- in order to maximize the use of the bioclimatic potential of each region, territorial allocation and creation of specialized commodity zones. in this case, it will be necessary to improve the production of the most appropriate type of production (grain, vegetables, melon crops, etc.) in different regions.

The main ways to implement this policy include increasing the industrial intensity of production, ensuring the quality of products and implementing the necessary volume of production. Such a policy also provides the necessary tools to support the income of commodity producers and create opportunities for them to carry out simple or expanded reproduction.

All this is directly related to investing in agriculture and its effective development. Therefore, attracting additional financial and material resources in the local area should be one of the most important tasks of territorial executive authorities. These resources can be provided mainly through the state budget, extra-budgetary funds, own funds of enterprises, loans provided by banks, foreign investors and other financial sources.

Investment in agriculture is of great importance, as it is necessary not only to increase production, but also to improve the quality of agricultural products, create new jobs and ensure economic stability. Effective management of all financial resources is very important to maintain the stability of the food market and supply the domestic market with a sufficient number of quality products. At the same time, this process serves not only economic interests, but also to improve the living standards of the population, solve social problems in rural areas.

In order to use funds as efficiently as possible, it is necessary to differentiate investment areas by region, culture, technological cycle and time period. It is necessary to determine the priority areas of investment policy in each region and correlate them with the specific characteristics of a particular territory, the level of development of farms in it, the actual state of the material and technical base, etc.

A prerequisite for regulating the production and sale of food products should be not the regulation of the market as a whole, but the regulation of each individual type of market (for example, the production and sale of feed, barley and oats can be regulated together), which will ensure increased targeted use of resources. At the same time, large-scale measures to regulate a particular type of product should not apply to the entire area of its cultivation, but should mainly concern only those zones specialized in the commercial production of this crop, improving the location of production.

State policy should be based on a complete and accurate analysis of the current situation in the development of the domestic food market. This process should be aimed at ensuring food security, meeting national economic needs through maximum use of the country's domestic production potential. It is necessary to determine the need for food products, including taking into account different periods and economic conditions. In this process, it is very important to assess the actual state of the market, identify existing opportunities, and consider development prospects.

It is also of great importance to strengthen interregional ties and develop a system of practical actions, taking into account the current market conditions for each period. This, in turn, will contribute to the sustainable development of the domestic market, optimize the distribution of resources and products between different regions, as well as improve the quality and availability of food products. This policy of the state will allow for the effective orientation of its

production capacities and the balanced development of the market, as a result of which the needs of the population will be fully and qualitatively satisfied.

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